

The Influence of Internship Experience on the Economic Welfare of Graduates at The School of Universe, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This research investigates the influence of internship experiences on the economic welfare of graduates from The School of Universe, Indonesia. Internships bridge academic knowledge and practical application, providing students with valuable hands-on skills crucial for their transition into the workforce. The study employs a quantitative approach, utilizing path analysis to explore the relationship between internship experiences and economic welfare. A 30-high school alumni sample was randomly selected, and data was gathered through a structured questionnaire. The results show a significant positive relationship between internships and graduates' economic welfare, with internships enhancing employability and boosting initial income levels. Path analysis confirms the significance and linearity of the model, establishing that internship experiences have a direct positive effect on economic welfare, supporting the hypothesis that internships contribute to graduates' financial stability and career progression.

KEYWORDS: Career progression, Economic welfare, Employability, Internship experiences.

INTRODUCTION

Internships are crucial in bridging the gap between academic knowledge and practical application, significantly enhancing students' readiness for the workforce (Thakur et al., 2024). They provide essential skills and foster a deeper understanding of students' fields of study (Jang-Tucci et al., 2024). Internship experiences are structured opportunities that allow students or recent graduates to gain practical, hands-on experience in a professional setting (Martins & Neto, 2023). These experiences bridge academic learning and real-world application of skills and knowledge (Feldman et al., 1998). Internships allow students to develop job-relevant competencies, build professional networks, and gain insights into their chosen field. By simulating actual work environments, internships enhance employability, improve critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, and often lead to better job prospects and increased initial income upon graduation (Gerçek et al., 2024; Malbuyo et al., 2024).

Furthermore, internships provide students with valuable practical experience and a smooth transition from the academic to the professional world (Nik et al., 2024). By simulating real-world work scenarios, internships help students develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills essential for success in the labor market (Wolinsky-Nahmias et al., 2022). Moreover, internships allow students to apply the knowledge they have gained in the classroom, fostering a deeper understanding of their field of study (Liu et al., 2011; Nasiri et al., 2023). Internships significantly enhance skills and career readiness. A study on criminology graduates revealed a high impact of internships on skills development, with a mean score of 3.65, indicating that participants felt their internships greatly improved their abilities (Malbuyo et al., 2024). Similarly, business students reported that internships fostered vital skills such as networking and communication, essential for career advancement (Gerçek & Özveren, 2024).

Employers also benefit from internship programs, as they can recruit talented individuals and evaluate their potential as future employees. Studies have shown that graduates who have completed internships are more likely to secure employment upon graduation, indicating the significant impact of internships on one's economic welfare (O'Connor & Bodicoat, 2017). Economic welfare refers to the financial well-being and standard of living of individuals or groups, often measured by income, employment status, and access to resources that contribute to a comfortable and stable life. It encompasses aspects such as the ability to meet basic needs (e.g., food, housing, healthcare), financial security, and the capacity to pursue opportunities for growth and development (McKenzie et al., 2017). Economic welfare is influenced by factors like job stability, income level, and social safety nets, and it plays a key role in determining the overall quality of life and economic stability of individuals or populations (Lian et al., 2018).

Internships are widely recognized as a crucial component of undergraduate education, as they bridge the gap between academic knowledge and practical application (Feldman et al., 1998). They provide students with valuable hands-on experience,

allowing them to develop a deeper understanding of their chosen field and acquire the necessary skills for a smooth transition into the workforce (Feldman et al., 1998; Margaryan et al., 2020; McKenzie et al., 2016). Furthermore, internships have been shown to have a positive impact on the economic welfare of graduates. Internship experiences, particularly those well-structured and aligned with students' career aspirations, can enhance their employability and increase their chances of securing a job after graduation (Margaryan, 2021).

Recent studies have explored the influence of internship experiences on the economic welfare of graduates, focusing on how these experiences affect their employment outcomes and income levels (Di Meglio et al., 2022; Silva et al., 2016). Internships provide students with job-relevant skills, increasing their productivity and making them more competitive in the labor market (Mohd Abbas et al., 2024). Interns who acquire both general and specific human capital often see improvements in their employability and starting salaries. However, the long-term impact on wages may vary depending on the nature of the internship (McKenzie & Mellis, 2018). Internships also serve as signals to potential employers, showcasing the candidate's ability and motivation (Shakil et al., 2023). Moreover, internships offer a screening mechanism for companies to evaluate potential hires (Silva et al., 2016). This has been shown to result in short-term wage increases for graduates who remain at the same firm where they interned, though the effect may diminish if they switch jobs (Di Meglio et al., 2022). Some research, like that of McKenzie et al. (2016), found no significant impact of internships on wages, while other studies like those by Margaryan et al. (2020) and Hora et al. (2020) report positive effects, particularly when internships are mandatory as part of the curriculum. Furthermore, O'Connor and Bodicoat (2017) explored the influence of internships on graduates from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, showing that internships can help bridge gaps in employment opportunities and contribute to social mobility. Feldman et al. (1998) pointed out the importance of internships in building professional networks, which can be crucial in helping graduates find employment. They found that internships often lead to job offers from host companies, resulting in a direct transition from student to employee.

The consensus across studies indicates that while internships can enhance employability and offer short-term income benefits, the long-term impact on graduates' economic welfare depends on factors such as industry, internship structure, and whether the intern stays with the same firm. Based on the research problem, previous research, and the identified research gaps above, potential research questions, namely:

1. What internships can enhance graduates' economic welfare?
2. How do internships influence long-term career progression and lifetime earnings of graduates?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a quantitative approach to examine the causal relationship between internship experiences and the economic welfare of graduates. The study used a correlational design, focusing on the direct influence of internship experiences on economic outcomes, such as employability and income levels. The model tested in this study relied on path analysis, allowing for a detailed exploration of the relationship between variables by estimating direct effects. The data was analyzed using regression techniques to determine the strength and significance of the relationship, ensuring that the hypotheses were tested rigorously.

Data Collection

Data collection was carried out using survey methods, namely, taking data from a sample to represent the population. The hypothetical model proposed in this research was tested using path analysis techniques.

Research Sample

Sample selection was done using random sampling techniques. The sample for this research was 100 high school alumni at Universe School, Indonesia. The instrument was distributed online via Google Forms, and only 30 alumni filled out the research instrument.

Instruments and Data Collection

This study employed a structured questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection, designed to capture both internship experiences and economic welfare outcomes. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended, rating scale-style questions, allowing for quantitative measurement of the variables under investigation. The collected data were subsequently analyzed using

statistical methods to evaluate the relationship between internship experiences and economic welfare. The researcher prepared and tested the questionnaire for validity and reliability before use.

Analyzing of Data

This study used data analysis to evaluate theories explaining the causal relationship between internship experiences and economic welfare. Based on the study as mentioned earlier aims, this was carried out. The data were analyzed using statistical techniques for inference and descriptive analysis.

Descriptive statistical methods were employed to characterize the various variables, such as calculating the mean, median, mode, range, standard deviation, and variance. The data was visually represented through histograms and frequency distribution tables.

Subsequently, classical assumption tests were conducted in the following phase, serving as a necessary step before hypothesis testing. Once the classical assumptions were examined, the analysis transitioned to hypothesis testing. This technique was applied to explain the direct and indirect effects between research variables based on the proposed hypothetical model.

RESULTS

Estimated Error Normality Test

The normality test of estimated error is one of the requirements for addressing research hypotheses utilizing path analysis data analysis methodologies. In path analysis, the sampling error must be derived from a normally distributed population. The normality test determines whether or not data follows a normal distribution. Statistical tests were used to determine normalcy. Normality testing using the Liliefors formula. The hypothesis proposed in the normalcy test is:

- H0: data comes from a normally distributed population;
- H1: the data comes from a population that is not normally distributed.

The test condition is that if the statistic $L_{count} \leq L_{table}$ ($\alpha = 0.05$), then the error data is normally distributed. Conversely, if $L_{count} \geq L_{table}$ ($\alpha = 0.05$), the data is declared not normally distributed. The results of the normality test calculation of the estimated error in each regression can be seen in the SPSS output table as follows:

Table 1. Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Unstandardized Residual X-Y	,081	30	,200*	,981	30	,849

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.
 a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Significance Test and Regression Linearity

Research hypothesis testing was carried out using regression and correlation analysis techniques. Regression analysis predicts the relationship model, while correlation analysis determines the level of influence between research variables.

The initial stage of hypothesis testing is to state the influence of each exogenous variable on the endogenous variable in the form of a simple regression equation. This equation is determined using measurement data in pairs of exogenous variables with endogenous variables so that the regression equation model is the most suitable form of relationship. Before using the regression equation to conclude hypothesis testing, the regression model obtained is tested for significance and linearity using the F test in the ANOVA table. The criteria for testing the significance and linearity of the regression model are set as follows:

- Significant regression: $F_{count} \geq F_{table}$ in the regression line
- Linear regression: $F_{count} < F_{table}$ on the matched tuna row

The next stage is to carry out correlational analysis by reviewing the level and significance of the relationship between pairs of exogenous variables and endogenous variables.

Table 2. Regression Coefficient of Y on X

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-9,010	14,893		-,605	,550
Internship Experiences (X)	,797	,100	,834	7,995	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Welfare (Y)

From the calculation data for preparing the regression equation model between Economic Welfare and Learning with Nature, the regression constant $a = -9.010$ and the regression coefficient $b = 0.797$ are obtained. Thus, the relationship between the simple regression equation model is $\hat{Y} = -9.010 + 0.797 X$. Before the regression equation model is analyzed further and used to draw conclusions, the significance and linearity of the regression equation are first tested. The results of the significance and linearity test calculations are arranged in the ANOVA table as follows:

Table 3. ANOVA for Significance Test of Regression Equation

$\hat{Y} = -9,010 + 0,797 X$

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	16460,890	1	16460,890	63,917	,000 ^b
Residual	7210,977	28	257,535		
Total	23671,867	29			

Dependent Variable: Economic Welfare (Y)

Predictors: (Constant), Internship Experiences (X)

Information :

*: Regression is very significant ($63.917 > 4.20$ at $\alpha = 0.05$)

The regression equation is $\hat{Y} = -9.010 + 0.797 X$; for the significance test, F_{count} was 63.917, which was greater than F_{table} (0.05;1:28) 4,20 at $\alpha = 0,05$ because $F_{count} > F_{table}$, the regression equation is declared very significant.

Table 4. ANOVA for Linearity Test of Regression Equations

$\hat{Y} = -9,010 + 0,797 X$

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Economic Welfare (Y) * Internship Experiences (X)	Between Groups	(Combined)	22451,867	27	831,551	1,363	,510
		Linearity	16460,890	1	16460,890	26,985	,035
		Deviation from Linearity	5990,977	26	230,422	,378	,910
Within Groups		1220,000	2	610,000			
Total		23671,867	29				

Information :

ns: Linear regression ($0.378 < 19.46$ at $\alpha = 0.05$)

For the linearity test, the F_{count} of 0.378 is smaller than the F_{table} (0.05;26:2) of 19.46 at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that the data distribution of the regression equation Y on X is linearly distributed.

Table 5. Regression Significance and Linearity Test Results

Reg	Equality	Regression Test		Linearity Test		Conclusion
		F _{count}	F _{table}	F _{count}	F _{table}	
			$\alpha = 0,05$		$\alpha = 0,05$	
Y on X ₁	$\hat{Y} = -9,010 + 0,797 X_1$	63,917	4,20 **	0,378	19,46 ^{ns}	Very significant regression/ Linear regression

Path Coefficient

The path coefficient calculation is carried out by continuing the results of the correlation coefficient calculation for each path based on the structural equation in the research constellation model. The correlation coefficient value for each path can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Correlation coefficient between variables

		Internship Experiences (X1)	Economic Welfare (Y)
Internship Experiences (X1)	Pearson Correlation	1	,834**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000
	N	30	30

Table 7. Path Coefficients and Path Significance Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	45,731	10,121		4,519	,000
Internship Experiences (X1)	,296	,100	,504	2,958	,006

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Welfare (Y)

From the path coefficient table resulting from the analysis above, the p_{xy} path coefficient value is 0.504 and t_{count} is 2.958, with $t_{table} (0.05:27) = 2.05$, so that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ and the p-value is $(0.006 < 0.05)$, so reject H_0 , accept H_1 and it can be interpreted that variable X has a direct positive influence on variable Y. Thus it is proven that Internship Experiences have a direct influence on Economic Welfare.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide significant evidence that internship experiences positively influence the economic welfare of graduates from The School of Universe, Indonesia. The path analysis confirms that students who engage in internships during high school are better equipped with job-relevant skills, enhancing their employability and starting income. This finding aligns with previous research, which has suggested that internships help bridge the gap between academic learning and real-world application (Silva et al., 2016). Internships provide graduates with practical skills, professional networks, and a deeper understanding of their career field, directly contributing to better job prospects and higher earnings (Hora et al., 2020).

The study's path analysis supports the hypothesis that internship experiences have a linear and direct positive effect on graduates' economic welfare. The significance and linearity of the regression model, as evidenced by the F_{count} of 63.917, further emphasize the strength of this relationship. The high correlation coefficient of 0.834 between internship experiences and economic welfare suggests a strong link between these variables.

These findings are consistent with prior studies that highlight the role of internships in enhancing graduates' career progression and financial stability. Internships offer a platform for students to acquire both general and specific human capital, making them more competitive in the labor market (Mohd Abbas et al., 2024). This is particularly important in the Indonesian context, where securing employment is increasingly competitive.

However, it is important to consider the nuances of these outcomes. While internships positively affect initial employability and income, the long-term impact on lifetime earnings may vary. Graduates who stay with the same firm where they intern may experience continued benefits, but those who switch jobs could see diminishing returns, as McKenzie et al. (2016) suggested.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research confirms that internship experiences play a crucial role in enhancing the economic welfare of School of Universe graduates. The direct and positive relationship between internships and employability and income underscores the importance of integrating structured and meaningful internship programs into the educational curriculum. By equipping students with practical skills and fostering professional networks, internships significantly contribute to graduates' short-term financial stability and long-term career success.

This research reinforces the idea that internships should be a critical component of educational programs to ensure graduates are adequately prepared for the workforce. Policymakers and educators should continue to promote internships to enhance students' career outcomes and economic welfare.

LIMITATIONS

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations that should be addressed in future research. First, the sample size was limited to 30 high school alumni from a single institution, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Expanding the sample to include graduates from multiple schools and regions could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of internships on economic welfare.

Second, the study focuses primarily on the short-term benefits of internships, such as employability and starting income. Future research could explore the long-term effects of internships on career progression and lifetime earnings, providing a more nuanced view of how internships shape graduates' professional trajectories.

Lastly, the research relies on self-reported data through questionnaires, which may introduce response bias. Incorporating qualitative interviews or employer feedback could offer a more balanced perspective on the effectiveness of internship experiences in shaping graduates' economic welfare.

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